

High School Graduates' IT Skills and Employers' Needs in the Telecommunications Sector: A Saudi Perspective

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Abstract

As Saudi Arabia continues its rapid digital transformation under Vision 2030, the telecoms industry has emerged as one of its fastest-growing sectors. However, there is a skills gap between IT education in Saudi high schools and the practical knowledge that telecom requires, especially for entry-level positions. The purpose of this study is to detect IT skill inadequacies among Saudi high school graduates and to recommend curriculum revisions that are more in line with telecom requirements. A data-oriented approach was taken, using insights collected from surveys of telecom specialists, educators, and recent high school graduates. The findings demonstrate significant gaps in practical IT skills, particularly hands-on experience, limiting graduates' career opportunities in the telecoms industry. Based on these findings, the research advises curriculum reforms and tailored training programs to provide students with the technical and practical skills required for entry-level positions, improving both employability and operational efficiency in the telecom sector.

Keywords

Digital transformation, Telecommunications industry, High school curriculum, IT skills gap, Workforce readiness.

1. Introduction

Saudi Arabia is undergoing a significant transformation through its Vision 2030 initiative, which aims to diversify the economy and drive growth across key sectors such as tourism, entertainment, and technology. The telecommunications industry, in particular, is one of the fastest-growing sectors, fuelled by the nation's focus on digital transformation [1-2].

As Saudi Arabia advances, the demand for skilled labour is increasing, and numerous job opportunities are emerging for both university and high school graduates, including those who do not pursue higher education. Data shows that 139,369 Saudis employed in various sectors hold only a high school diploma, underscoring the critical role of high school education in preparing students for the workforce. Additionally, around 7% of high school graduates in 2017 were not accepted into universities, highlighting the need for high school programs to better prepare students for immediate entry into the job market [3].

Despite Saudi Arabia's strong ranking in regional technology skills, as reported in the Coursera Global Skills Report 2023, the current educational system does not adequately address the practical requirements of the workforce [3]. Specifically, the existing IT curriculum in Saudi high schools is not aligned with industry needs, particularly in the rapidly evolving telecommunications sector. Recent reports show that many high school graduates entering the labour market lack essential IT skills, such as cybersecurity and IT support, creating a significant skills gap. This gap limits graduates' employability and increases the training burden on employers.

This research focuses on identifying the gap between the IT skills taught in Saudi high schools and the practical competencies required by telecom companies. It highlights the missing skills in

the current curriculum and recommends targeted reforms that integrate practical experience with theoretical knowledge. These changes aim to better align education with industry demands, ultimately enhancing employability and reducing the need for extensive post-hire training. By addressing this gap, the study supports Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 in fostering a digitally skilled workforce and driving economic growth.

A data-oriented approach was used in this study, collecting insights from telecom professionals, educators, and recent high school graduates. Surveys were designed to assess the current state of IT education in high schools and gather feedback on the specific skills that are most in demand in the telecommunications industry. The findings from these surveys will be used to inform recommendations for curriculum reforms and training programs aimed at aligning educational outcomes with industry requirements.

The primary contribution of this research is the identification of critical IT skills gaps among Saudi high school graduates, particularly in areas like cybersecurity, IT support, and hands-on technical experience. By analysing these gaps through a data-driven approach, the study offers actionable recommendations for curriculum changes that will help align high school IT education with the practical needs of the telecom industry. This not only highlights areas for improvement but also proposes a clear pathway to better prepare students for entry-level roles in telecommunications, supporting Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 goals of fostering a technologically skilled workforce.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 reviews existing literature on IT education and the skills gap in the telecommunications industry. Section 3 outlines the research methodology, including the data collection and analysis methods used to identify specific IT skills gaps among high school graduates. Section 4 presents the study's findings and offers recommendations for curriculum changes. It also discusses the broader implications of these findings and proposes directions for future research and reforms. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study by summarizing the key takeaways and highlighting the importance of aligning high school IT education with industry needs to enhance employability and support the nation's digital transformation.

2. Related Work (Literature Review)

This study examines the crucial role of information technology (IT) education in Saudi Arabia, focusing on the telecommunications industry and the evolving job market demands. As the country implements its Vision 2030 initiative to diversify the economy and enhance workforce employability, it is essential to understand the current landscape of IT education. The review analyses key themes surrounding IT skills requirements, existing curricula, and the alignment (or misalignment) between educational outcomes and industry demands. The primary objective is to identify research gaps related to the IT competencies necessary for success in entry-level positions within the telecommunications sector.

A study by Purwanto et al. [4] investigates essential 21st-century skills required for college graduates transitioning to the workforce. Their findings highlight a significant skills gap, underscoring the need for education systems to foster in-demand skills such as communication, collaboration, and problem-solving [5]. However, the study relies on job advertisements from only two websites, which may skew the data. Future research should explore how employers formulate job ads and consider diverse sources. Similarly, Scaffidi [6] identifies the technical and soft skills valued by employers of computer science graduates in the Pacific Northwest. The study uncovers deficiencies in collaboration, communication, and software testing skills, advocating for curriculum modifications to better align with employer needs. Limitations include a small sample size and potential biases in qualitative analysis. Future research should employ larger-scale surveys for validation like [7].

Tyran and Tyran [8] develop and evaluate a "Professional Readiness" program designed to enhance relational and professional skills among Information Systems (IS) students. This study

addresses the challenge of preparing IS students for their careers by fostering often-neglected skills in traditional curricula. The authors note that many students view professional preparedness as "common sense," underestimating its significance while also highlighting resource limitations and curricular inflexibility for professionalism training. Their pilot program, implemented as an extracurricular resource, proves effective in engaging students in career-relevant activities. Findings indicate the necessity of promoting professional preparation to enhance job prospects, though focusing on a pilot program limits the generalizability of results and studies [9-10]. The authors recommend further research to explore the program's long-term impact and potential in other disciplines.

Yoder et al. [11] investigate the relationship between social and emotional learning (SEL) and workforce development, identifying essential skills for labour market success. Their study reveals a significant misalignment between SEL competencies developed in K-12 education and those sought by employers, particularly in communication, collaboration, and problem-solving. However, relying on surveys and job postings may not capture the full complexity of employer needs. Future research should examine the impact of specific SEL interventions on student success across various sectors. The study titled "Promoting Digital Skills for Austrian Employees through a MOOC: Results and Lessons Learned from Design and Implementation" [12] explores developing digital skills among employees through a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). The research assesses the MOOC's usage and impact, revealing its effectiveness in addressing the need for digital skills amid increasing digitalisations. The findings indicate that the MOOC successfully upskilled 500 employees, with positive feedback on content and delivery. However, limitations include the specific focus on one MOOC and its early implementation, potentially restricting generalizability. Future research should adapt digital skills frameworks to various settings and explore diverse educational strategies.

Research on employers' perceptions of employability skills in [13] reveals a mismatch between high school curricula and industry expectations. The study underscores the necessity of integrating personal qualities and critical thinking into K-12 education. The authors recommend expanding research to include a broader range of sectors for more generalised insights. My research aligns with this by identifying specific IT skills required in Saudi Arabia, which are vital for improving job readiness and overall business efficiency in the telecommunications sector. In an international context, a study in [14] investigates employability skills from employers' perspectives in Bangladesh, revealing a gap between graduates' skills and employer expectations, despite high unemployment rates. Essential competencies identified include communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and technical skills. The authors recommend collaboration between universities and businesses to align curricula with market demands, suggesting the Education Ministry facilitate integrating these skills into programs. However, the limitations include a focus on established firms, which restricts the generalizability of findings.

The role of digital technologies in transforming education amid the Fourth Industrial Revolution is explored in [15-17]. This study emphasises the need to integrate these technologies to bridge the skills gap, particularly concerning the Internet of Things (IoT) and digital literacy. While digital technologies can enhance learning experiences, their lack of integration in current education systems limits potential benefits. The authors recommend developing strategies for more holistic technology integration. The study in [18] examines the skills gap among accounting graduates, stressing the need to integrate non-technical skills—such as communication and interpersonal abilities—into the curriculum. This disconnect between technical knowledge and broader employability skills necessitates improved collaboration among educators and industry stakeholders. The authors recommend replicating their research in various contexts to compare findings. The emphasis on non-technical skills aligns with findings in [19], demonstrating a significant correlation between high school coursework and college readiness. This study highlights the necessity of evaluating

educational policies and recommends further research to establish causal relationships between course selection and academic performance. A systematic review in [20] analyses Education 4.0 components, emphasising the need for frameworks that promote innovation in teaching and learning strategies. The study suggests further exploration of advanced technologies in education to mitigate disparities exacerbated by the pandemic.

Finally, the study "What Skills Do Students Need? A Multi-Year Study of IT/IS Knowledge and Skills in Demand by Employers" [21] aims to identify current technological and skill demands in the IT/IS sector through employer surveys. Findings reveal a high demand for software development, business analysis, and communication skills, emphasising the necessity of incorporating web development and data analytics throughout educational programs. While the study does not specify limitations, potential weaknesses include the generalizability of findings and the rapidly evolving technological landscape. The authors recommend continued monitoring of skill requirements. This section highlights the critical role of IT education in Saudi Arabia, particularly concerning the telecommunications industry. It underscores significant gaps in existing research related to the necessary competencies for high school graduates, revealing a misalignment between educational outcomes and industry demands. The review emphasises the need for curriculum reforms to integrate essential skills, including both technical and non-technical abilities, to enhance employability. My research aims to address these gaps by providing actionable recommendations that align IT education with the practical needs of the telecommunications sector, contributing to the broader goal of improving job readiness among high school graduates in Saudi Arabia.

3. Methods

The primary objective of my research is to identify the gap between the IT skills taught in Saudi high schools and the practical skills required by the telecommunications industry. This study aims to provide actionable recommendations for curriculum adjustments and targeted training programs to align education with industry needs. To achieve this, a data-oriented approach [22] is employed, focusing on gathering insights from key stakeholders in both the education and telecommunications sectors. Surveys are used as the primary data collection method, targeting high school graduates, teachers, and telecom professionals, including HR personnel, trainers, and new employees. The research design revolves around a survey-based data collection method. The study is structured in several steps to ensure a comprehensive analysis:

- **Survey Design:**

The survey is tailored to capture the perspectives of two main groups: telecom professionals and educators. It includes both quantitative and qualitative elements, such as multiple-choice, Likert scale, and open-ended questions. This mixed-methods approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of the skills gap, combining numerical data with detailed feedback. Two surveys are designed, one for the telecom sector and another for the education sector, to explore differences in expectations and preparedness.

- **Target Participants:**

The first survey targets telecom professionals, including HR staff, trainers, and new employees in Saudi telecommunications companies. The second survey targets IT teachers in high schools and recent high school graduates. Each group provides valuable insights into the curriculum and the skills required for entry-level positions in the telecom industry. The aim is to gather data from at least 300 participants across both sectors to ensure statistical reliability and represent stakeholder diversity.

- **Survey Distribution:**

The surveys were distributed through a variety of channels to ensure comprehensive coverage and a representative sample of responses. Telecom companies played a key role by distributing the surveys internally to their employees, including human resources staff, trainers, and newly hired employees. In the education sector, the Ministry of Education, particularly the Development and Transformation Department in the Eastern Province, facilitated the distribution of surveys to secondary school teachers specializing in computer science. These surveys were disseminated through official educational portals and networks, ensuring they reached a wide range of relevant participants.

Additionally, King Faisal University contributed by sending the surveys to first-year students who had recently graduated from secondary schools. This approach ensured that the views of both recent graduates and educators were captured, providing a broad perspective on the alignment between education and industry needs. These carefully selected distribution channels were critical for reaching a diverse and representative sample of approximately 750 participants, as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2. Each phase of the study targeted distinct participant groups, allowing the research to collect valuable insights from both the telecommunications and education sectors, providing a holistic view of the IT skills gap.

Q17 - Please select your role within your telecom company:

Fig. 1. Number of participants from telecom company

Q17 - Please select your role within the education sector:

366 Responses

Fig. 2. Number of participants from the education sector

1. Telecom Sector Survey:

This survey gathers insights from HR professionals, trainers, and new employees. HR professionals and trainers offer perspectives on the specific IT skills they look for when hiring and training new staff. New employees provide feedback on how well their high school education prepared them for their roles. Key areas of inquiry include IT competencies, perceived skill gaps, and suggestions for improvement.

2. Education Sector Survey:

The second survey focuses on high school IT teachers and recent graduates. Teachers provide feedback on the current IT curriculum, teaching methods, and the challenges they face in preparing students for the workforce. Graduates offer insights into their educational experiences and how well their training aligns with the skills needed in the job market, especially within the telecom sector.

Once the data is collected, it undergoes a rigorous analysis process.

1. **Data Processing:**

All responses are compiled into structured datasets using software CSV files. The data is organised into distinct groups based on participant demographics to ensure clarity. Before analysis, the data is processed to remove any incomplete or irrelevant responses, providing only high-quality data is included.

2. **Quantitative Analysis:**

The quantitative data is analysed using a statistical tool using Qualtricsxm. Multiple-choice and Likert scale responses are statistically evaluated to identify common trends, such as prevalent IT skill gaps and the alignment (or misalignment) between curriculum content and employer expectations. Descriptive statistics, cross-tabulations, and frequency analysis are employed to explore the relationships between the different variables.

3. **Qualitative Analysis:**

Open-ended responses are coded thematically to extract recurring themes. Thematic coding helps in identifying key areas such as “practical IT skills,” “curriculum alignment,” “employer expectations,” and “student preparedness.” This analysis allows for the extraction of rich, nuanced insights that quantitative data may overlook, offering recommendations for improvement.

To ensure the reliability and validity of the findings, multiple data sources from educators and telecom professionals are used for cross-validation, with surveys designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative data. Distributing surveys through official channels ensures a representative sample. However, the study has limitations, including the restricted depth of data compared to methods like interviews, potential lack of detail in open-ended responses, and a sample size that may not fully represent the diversity of the sectors. Additionally, rapid changes in both the telecom industry and IT education could quickly render the findings outdated.

This research adopts a data-oriented methodology to explore the alignment between high school IT education and the needs of the telecom industry in Saudi Arabia. The methodology includes designing and distributing surveys to key stakeholders, processing and analysing both quantitative and qualitative data and validating findings through cross-sector comparison. By identifying the specific IT skills gaps and assessing the misalignment between education and industry demands, this research aims to propose actionable curriculum changes and training programs to better equip students for careers in telecommunications.

4. Results and Discussion

Based on surveys data collected from telecom professionals, trainers, HR officials, and new workers, numerous critical observations about the IT skills gap and curriculum misalignment in Saudi high schools have emerged.

1. IT Skills Gap among High School Graduates:

The survey data revealed that a significant portion of high school graduates entering the telecom industry lack essential technical skills. Notably:

- **Lack of Practical Skills:** A large percentage of respondents 35% cited a lack of technical skills as the primary reason for rejecting candidates with a high school IT background.

Q16 - What is the most common reason for rejecting candidates with a high school IT background? - Selected Choice

Fig. 3. Reason for rejecting applicants

- Hands-On Experience: 83% of respondents stressed the importance of hands-on experience (e.g., labs and projects) in evaluating a candidate's readiness for telecom roles
- Q20_2 - How important is hands-on experience (e.g., labs, projects) in evaluating a candidate's readiness for telecom roles?

Fig. 4. The importance of practical work

However, high school graduates often lack this exposure.

- Foundational IT Knowledge: High school graduates frequently need retraining in basic IT concepts. For instance, 58% of respondents indicated that they frequently have to retrain new graduates on foundational knowledge.

Q20_1 - How satisfied are you with the general IT knowledge of high school graduates?

Fig. 5. Participants' satisfaction with IT information

- Cybersecurity and IT Support: The most cited areas where new graduates require further training are cybersecurity 46.46% and IT support 43.43%.

- **Real-World Relevance:** 40.54% of respondents felt that high schools are not preparing students well for real-world tasks, they often encountered tasks at work that were not covered in their high school IT education.

Q31_1 - How prepared did you feel for your job in terms of technical skills when you started?

Field	Choice Count
Not prepared at all	45
Slightly prepared	24
Moderately prepared	31
Very prepared	11

Fig. 9. Students feel ready when they start work.

3. Suggested Curriculum Improvements:

Survey participants made several recommendations for improving the IT curriculum in Saudi high schools:

- **Practical Training:** Many recommended introducing more hands-on training methods, such as lab-based learning and simulations, to help students gain practical experience.

Q5 - What training tools do you use most frequently? - Selected Choice

Fig. 10. Most used tools in training

- **Industry-Specific Training:** Many of the respondents stressed the critical need for high schools to integrate industry-specific IT training into the curriculum.

Q20_5 - How critical is it for high schools to include industry-specific IT training in their curriculum?

Fig. 11. The importance of integrating training into curricula

4. Challenges in Transitioning from School to Work:

New employees reported challenges in adapting to the telecom industry's requirements due to a lack of practical exposure in high school:

- **Lack of Job-Ready Skills:** The transition from school to work was challenging for most graduates. Only 18% found it "very easy" or "easy," while the majority found it "moderate" or "difficult."

Fig. 12. Easy transition from study to work

- **Inadequate Preparation for Specific Tasks:** Many graduates felt unprepared for job-specific tasks, particularly in areas like troubleshooting and network management, as these were not adequately covered in their high school IT education.

Q30 - What area of your job did you find most challenging due to a lack of prior training? - Selected Choice

Fig. 13. Areas most challenged by lack of training

- **Difficulty Applying Theory:** Graduates often struggle to apply theoretical knowledge in practical contexts. This was identified as one of the biggest challenges, with 36.36% of respondents highlighting this issue.

Q4 - What is the biggest challenge you face when training new high school graduates? - Selected Choice

Field	Choice Count
Lack of foundational knowledge	19
Difficulty in applying theory to practice	72
Resistance to learning new skills	75
Time constraints	32

Fig. 14. The biggest challenge students face during their training

5. Importance of Certifications and Continuous Learning:

- **Industry Certifications:** Many of the respondents felt that having certifications like Microsoft Certified Azure Fundamental, CompTIA A+, or Cisco CCNA was important when hiring new graduates.

Q1 - Which IT certifications do you prefer when hiring new high school graduates? - Selected Choice

Fig. 15. Most requested certificates

- **Continuous Learning:** Graduates were encouraged to pursue further learning and certifications to stay competitive in the field. Many recommended online courses and self-learning as critical components of continuous development.

Q29 - Which of the following best describes the additional training you received after joining the company? - Selected Choice

Field	Choice Count
Formal classroom training	9
On-the-job learning	37
Online courses	38
Mentorship	26
Other (please specify):	3

Fig. 16. Additional training after joining the company

According to replies from teachers and recent high school graduates, numerous significant observations concerning the present level of IT education in Saudi high schools have emerged. The following study summarises the key results about the curriculum's efficacy, the application of practical skills, and the obstacles experienced by students and teachers.

1. Effectiveness of High School IT Education:

The data indicates that while some students feel moderately prepared for further education, the curriculum is not adequately equipping them with practical, industry-relevant IT skills.

- **Preparation for Further Education:**
 - 46% of high school graduates felt that their IT education only prepared them "somewhat effectively" for their further studies.
 - A relatively small portion 30% found the skills they acquired to be extremely or very applicable.

Q1 - How effectively did your high school IT education prepare you for your current academic studies?

Fig. 17. The impact of IT education on student preparation

- **Lack of Practical Emphasis:**

- Many students indicated that practical, hands-on learning experiences in their high school IT curriculum were rare. Most of the respondents stated that such experiences occurred "occasionally" or "rarely".

Q3 - 3. How often did your high school IT curriculum incorporate practical, hands-on learning experiences?

Fig. 18. The amount of practical application within the curricula

- Many respondents mentioned that their IT education's primary focus was theoretical understanding rather than practical application.

Q4 - 4. What would you say was the primary emphasis of your high school IT education? - Selected Choice

Fig. 19. The basic element of IT education

2. Satisfaction with Hands-On Training:

The survey results show a general dissatisfaction with the level of hands-on IT training provided in high schools.

- Dissatisfaction with Training:
 - Only 24.2% of students reported being "very satisfied" or "extremely satisfied" with the hands-on training they received in their IT classes.
 - This dissatisfaction was echoed in their feedback on the relevance of their training for real-world applications, with a significant portion of students feeling only "slightly satisfied".

Q6_2 - How satisfied are you with the hands-on training you received during your high school IT classes?

Field	Choice Count
Not satisfied at all	12
Slightly satisfied	34
Moderately satisfied	39
Very satisfied	22
Extremely satisfied	3

Fig. 20. Student satisfaction with the practical application in the classroom

3. Gaps in the IT Curriculum:

Educators identified several critical gaps in the current IT curriculum, which prevent students from being fully prepared for industry demands.

- Outdated Curriculum and Lack of Resources:
 - 33.71 % of educators highlighted that the IT curriculum is outdated and not aligned with current technological trends.
 - A lack of access to industry-standard tools and resources was another major challenge cited by 35.42% of respondents.
 - Limited classroom time for practical exercises was also identified as a key barrier to effective IT education, preventing students from gaining adequate hands-on experience.

Q19 - What challenges do you face in teaching practical IT skills? - Selected Choice

Field	Choice Count
Lack of resources	62
Outdated curriculum	59
Insufficient training	36
Limited classroom time	18

Fig. 21. What are the difficulties facing the practical application of IT?

4. Recommendations for Curriculum Enhancement:

Both students and educators suggested several improvements to better align the IT curriculum with industry needs.

- Integration of Real-World Scenarios:
 - 60 of educators emphasized the importance of incorporating real-world IT scenarios and projects into the curriculum to improve students' readiness for industry roles.

Q20_2 - How important is it to incorporate real-world IT scenarios into the classroom?

Fig. 22. How important is it to introduce real-world IT scenarios into the classroom?

- They recommended introducing more internship programs, mentorship opportunities, and collaborations with IT companies to provide students with practical exposure.

Q10 - In your opinion, how can high schools improve the integration of practical IT skills into their curricula?

Fig. 23. Things that improve the practical application of IT

5. Student Confidence and Real-World Application:

While some students reported confidence in their IT skills, many felt underprepared for real-world challenges.

- Confidence in IT Skills:

- Only 26.21% of students felt "very confident" in their IT skills compared to their peers, and many reported that the skills they learned in high school were not easily transferable to real-world problems.

Q6_4 - How confident are you in your IT skills compared to peers who did not receive formal IT education during high school?

Field	Choice Count
Not confident at all	20
Slightly confident	24
Moderately confident	31
Very confident	27
Extremely confident	7

Fig. 24. Students' Confidence in IT Knowledge Compared to Peers

- Common feedback from students included a lack of focus on critical areas such as cybersecurity, networking, and problem-solving, which are crucial in modern IT roles.

This study identified vital IT skills that Saudi high school graduates lack for entry-level telecom positions, including networking, cybersecurity, troubleshooting, and software management. These deficiencies highlight the gap between the theoretical IT education provided in schools and the practical needs of the telecom industry. To address this, recommendations include incorporating hands-on learning, offering industry-relevant certifications, and providing internships and job shadowing opportunities with telecom companies. The findings align with previous research, confirming the need for curriculum reforms to meet industry demands. However, this study adds value by focusing specifically on the telecom sector and offering targeted recommendations.

The implications are significant for both education and the telecom industry, suggesting the need for updated curricula and more vital industry collaboration. Despite these contributions, limitations include the reliance on surveys, the sample size, and the rapidly changing nature of the telecom industry, which could make the results quickly outdated. Future research should consider interviews or focus groups for richer insights, track the long-term impact of curriculum changes, and explore how the findings apply to other sectors.

5. Conclusions

Based on the findings and implications discussed throughout my study, it is clear that Saudi high school IT education is misaligned with the practical demands of the telecommunications sector. The study identified critical gaps in the curriculum, particularly in hands-on experience, cybersecurity, and IT support. These gaps hinder the employability of graduates and increase the training burden on telecom employers. By highlighting the need for curriculum reforms, the research emphasises the importance of integrating industry-relevant skills into high school IT education to better prepare students for entry-level roles in this rapidly evolving sector.

This study's implications are significant for the education system and the telecom industry. Equipping students with practical IT skills, such as networking and cybersecurity, will not only

enhance their job readiness but also contribute to the Kingdom's broader Vision 2030 goals of fostering a digitally literate workforce. Furthermore, the research calls for collaboration between educators and industry professionals to ensure the curriculum remains responsive to the telecom sector's dynamic needs.

Despite these contributions, the study is not without limitations. The reliance on surveys as the primary data collection method may have limited the depth of the insights obtained. Additionally, the rapidly changing nature of technology and the telecom industry could render the findings outdated over time. Future research should explore a broader range of data collection methods, including in-depth interviews, focus groups, and case studies with both educators and industry professionals. This approach would offer richer, more qualitative insights into the nuances of the skills gap, and help uncover the specific challenges faced by graduates transitioning into the workforce. Additionally, longitudinal studies are recommended to evaluate the long-term effects of curriculum changes, assessing whether reforms lead to improved career readiness and job placement in the telecommunications industry. There is also a need to further investigate how high school IT education can better integrate emerging technologies, such as AI, IoT, and cloud computing, to stay aligned with the evolving demands of the workforce. These technologies are crucial not just in telecommunications but across various industries, and future studies should examine how best to incorporate these into the curriculum. Lastly, exploring the scalability of industry-school partnerships will be key to fostering continuous learning. By building on the findings of this study, future research can guide the development of educational strategies that equip students with the practical skills needed to thrive in Saudi Arabia's digitally transforming economy, ultimately supporting the objectives of Vision 2030.

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Author's biography

Devoted to improving education quality, Munirah Almulhim develops effective teaching methodologies to address students' evolving needs. Her research explores the development of digital literacy skills and enhancing curricula for high schoolers and teachers. Her vision aligns with the importance of technological innovation in transforming traditional educational practices, particularly computer-based instruction.

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